

Correction

Correction: Comodi et al. Multi-Scale Minero-Chemical Analysis of Biomass Ashes: A Key to Evaluating Their Dangers vs. Benefits. *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 6052

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The authors would like to make the following corrections to the published paper [1]. The changes are as follows:

(1) Replacing the heading of “Section 2.2.5.” on page 3:

“EMPA Analysis”

with

“EMPA and LA-ICP-MS Analyses”

(2) The authors wish to add an explanation along with a reference in “Section 2.2.5.” on page 4.

Replacing the original version: The glass pellets obtained after the quenching were embedded with epoxy resin; the mounts were cut, ground, and highly polished down to a 1 µm grade diamond polishing paste.

with

The glass pellets obtained after the quenching were embedded with epoxy resin; the mounts were cut, ground, and highly polished down to a 1 µm grade diamond polishing paste. Minor and trace elements were analysed at the Department of Physics and Geology (Perugia University) by LA-ICP-MS using the analytical protocol reported in Ref. [25].

Adding a reference into the citation list: 25. Petrelli, M.; Morgavi, D.; Vetere, F.; Perugini, D. Elemental Imaging and Petro-Volcanological Applications of an Improved Laser Ablation Inductively Coupled Quadrupole Plasma Mass Spectrometry. *Period. Mineral.* 2016, doi:10.2451/2015PM0465.

(3) Replacing the caption of Table 4 on page 11:

Table 4. Minor elements (ppm), measured with EMPA, in the four samples (2, 3, 4, and 5).

with

Table 4. Minor elements (ppm) measured with LA-ICP-MS in the four samples (2, 3, 4, and 5).

Reference

1. Comodi, P.; Zucchini, A.; Susta, U.; Cambi, C.; Vivani, R.; Cavalaglio, G.; Cotana, F. Multi-Scale Minero-Chemical Analysis of Biomass Ashes: A Key to Evaluating Their Dangers vs. Benefits. *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 6052. [[CrossRef](#)]